

DETERMINING BIOLOGICAL EFFICIENCY OF SEED TREATMENT AGENTS AGAINST FUSARIUM ROOT ROT DISEASE OF MUNG BEAN

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This article reveals the results of the research conducted to study biological efficacy of fungicide seed treatment agents Fundazol 50% w.pow. (2.0 kg / t), Maxim XL 035 FS 3.5% c.s. (1.5-2.5 l / t) and Vitavax 200.75% w.pow. (4.0 kg / t) against fusarium root rot disease of mung bean. According to the results of our study, the highest biological efficiency was noted in Maxim XL 035 FS, 3.5% c.s. In the variant where this preparation was applied at a rate of 2.5 l / t, 455 seedlings sprouted, of which 48 became infected, the severity of the disease was 2.5% and the biological effectiveness of the preparation was 86.6%.

Key words: *mung bean, disease, root rot, fusarium, fungus, severity of disease, seed treatment agent, fungicide, biological efficacy.*

INTRODUCTION. The growing rate of the world's population year by year is causing increase in demand for plant protein day by day. Mung bean is grown on more than 158 million hectares in more than 100 countries and is one of the most protein-rich crops. According to the FAO, the annual yield of mung bean has been reduced by up to 40% as a result of damage caused by various fungal diseases¹. This crop plays a key role in meeting the demand of the world's population for food products, including protein, amino acids and carbohydrates.

Today, great attention is paid to the cultivation of cereals and legumes in our country, and the area under these crops is expanding. Furthermore, great opportunities have opened up for the development of farming and the efficient use of land. One of the most pressing issues today is protein production, which is to meet the need of humanity for protein. The role of legumes, especially mung bean, is great in solving this problem.

Root rot disease is one of the most common and major diseases of mung bean. To protect the seedlings from root rot, it is necessary to treat the mung bean seeds with seed treatments or seed dressings with protective functions before sowing. Finding seed treatment agents against fusarium root rot and other root rot diseases is a huge economic benefit.

¹<http://www.fao.org>

COMMENTS ON REFERENCES. As mung bean is a type of bean, its taxonomy is based on beans. There are more than 200 species of *Phaseolus*, of which about 20 species are used as crops, the rest are wild species. According to their origin, the species is divided into two (American and Asian) geographical groups. The American group includes the following common species: common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L), stem is hairy, erect or twining, its pod has 3-5 seeds, 1000 seeds weight is 200-400 g, seeds vary in color, from white to orange; runner bean (*Phaseolus multiflorus* Lam), stem is long twining, with white and red flowers, large seeds, 1000 seeds weight is 700-1200 g; tepary bean (*Phaseolus lunatus acatifolus* Gray L.), stem is hairy, broad, short, and flat, 2-3 seeds on the pods, rapidly shatter; lima bean (*Phaseolus lunatus* L) has annual and perennial forms, the flowers are small, the stem is broad, flat, there are 2-3 seeds in pod, the seed is large, white, sometimes in a different color [1].

It is known that most of the diseases found in plants are caused by phytopathogenic microorganisms. In this case, the phytopathogenic microorganism lives due to the use of nutrients in the living tissue of the plant [2].

Root rot disease of mung bean occurs in many mung bean growing countries around the world and has a major impact on plant productivity [7; 9].

The disease is caused by representatives of the family Fusarium, which belongs to the imperfect class of fungi. The root collar and root of plants infected with root rot turn reddish brown, then rot and the plant dies. Young seedlings are more affected by the disease. Disease is caused by *F. avenaceum* Sacc., *F. culmorum* Sacc. [6] and *Fusarium solani* (Mart.) Sacc. f. sp. *Phaseoli* (Burkholder) W.C. Snyder & H.N. Hans species [8]. As a result of increased moisture in the soil, the damage of the disease increases and the plants become sparse [12].

THE OBJECT AND METHODS OF RESEARCH. The experiments have been carried out on mung bean varieties "Navruz", "Kahrabo" and "Radost" included in the State Register. In the treatment of mung bean plant seeds, we tested the following fungicide seed treatment agents against root rot disease of many agricultural crops: Fundazol 50% w.pow. (2.0 kg / t), Maxim XL 035 FS, 3.5% c.s. (1.5-2.5 l / t). As standard variant was selected Vitavax 200.75% w.pow. (4.0 kg / t) preparation which gives good results in the fight against root rot disease of many crops.

At the experiment, the seeds were treated with seed treatments one month before sowing. The sown seeds germinated after 6-8 days. After the onset of mass damage of disease, records were conducted every 3 days [3;4;5;10;11].

RESEARCH RESULTS. As a result of our research, 386 seedlings sprouted from seeds sown in the treatment free variant, 120 of them became infected, the damage level increased by 31.1% and the severity of the disease increased to 18.6%.

The highest biological efficacy in our study was observed in Maxim XL 035 FS, 3.5% c.s. preparation. In the variant treated with this preparation at a rate of 1.5 l / t, out of 500 seeds sown, 448 pieces germinated, of which 55 were infected with root rot, the severity of the disease was 3.3% and the biological efficacy of the preparation was 82.3%. In the variant treated with this preparation at a rate of 2.5 l / t, 455 seedlings sprouted, of which 48 became infected, the severity of the disease was 2.5% and the biological efficiency of the preparation was 86.6%.

In the variant treated with Vitavax 200.75% w.pow. selected as a standard agent at the rate of 4.0 l / t, 436 seedlings sprouted, 60 of them became infected, the severity of the disease was 3.2% and the biological efficacy of the preparation was 82.8% (Table 1).

Table-1.

**Biological efficacy of fungicide seed treatment agents against
fusarium root rot**

No	Experimental variants	Using rate, l/t, kg/t	Number of sown seeds, pcs	Sprouted seedlings, pcs	Infected seedlings, pcs	Damage level,%	Disease severity,%	Biological efficacy,%
1	Fundazol, 50% w.pow.	2,0	500	412	62	15,0	4,2	77,4
2	Maxim XL 035 FS, 3,5% c.s.	1,5	500	448	55	12,3	3,3	82,3
		2,5	500	455	48	10,5	2,5	86,6
3	Vitavax 200 75% w.pow. (standard)	4,0	500	436	60	13,8	3,2	82,8
4	Control	-	500	386	120	31,1	18,6	-

The lowest result on biological efficacy (77.4%) among seed treatment agents was noted in Fundazol, 50% w.pow. When this preparation was used at a rate of 2.0 kg / t, the incidence of fusarium was found to be 15.0%, and the severity of the disease was 4.2%.

CONCLUSION. According to our research on pre-sowing treatment of seeds with seed treatment agents against fusarium root rot disease of mung bean plant, it can be concluded that when the seeds are treated with fungicide seed treatment agent Maxim XL 035 FS, 3.5% c.s. at a rate of 2.5 l / t before sowing, the severity of fusarium root rot disease is stopped by 86.6% and a high yield is obtained from the mung bean plant.

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